

Mining Zenodo: Data extraction and indexing of a research repository

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Mining Zenodo: Data extraction and indexing of a research repository

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Dedication

To my parents: Carolina and Sergio, and my sister, Alexia for their full and unconditional support.

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- My family

Abstract

The output of scientific publications is increasing steadily each year. Due to this scientific literature overload, an exhaustive research of a certain topic becomes overwhelming and researchers cannot get a solid grasp of all this valuable knowledge. Natural language processing and text mining have become essential to tackle this issue and provide a solution: a comprehensive, careful and accessible perspective on the knowledge contained in scientific publications. This work aims to take advantage of this opportunity and develop an application to extract and index part of the information contained in Zenodo, an open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program. The work will be based on the employment of the Dr Inventor tool (a text mining framework that enables the automated analysis of scientific publications) to support the extraction of specific information types from Zenodo's collection of research papers in order to allow semantic indexing, discourse classification and discovery. The application is meant to be a useful and helpful tool to ease the learning experience of researchers, students and more.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing; data mining; open-access repository; web application

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Over the last couple centuries, the number of articles and journals have both grown steadily. It has been estimated that approximately 2,5 million articles are published every year by journals all over the world [1]. Or, to portray it in a different way, a new scientific paper is being published every 13 seconds. In addition, growth has accelerated in the last few decades due to a persistent increase of scientific researchers [1]. The open access publishing model is also growing significantly, which leads to more information available to a larger number of researchers and interested peers.

Due to this scientific literature overload, an exhaustive research of a certain topic becomes overwhelming. The fact that researchers cannot get a solid grasp of all this valuable knowledge raises the importance of online scientific literature search engines (Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Springer,...) and automated engines that extract, enrich and summarize information from numerous scientific publications.

Natural language processing and text mining have become essential to tackle the issue presented above and to provide a solution: to facilitate a comprehensive, careful and accessible perspective on the knowledge contained in scientific publications.

Nevertheless, dealing with the enormous amount of data involved, the diversity of

topics and fields within the science community and the error rate of automated approaches are just a few of the challenges faced.

Consequently, a remarkable opportunity is presented: to apply these techniques and approaches to a collection of scientific papers from Zenodo, an open-access repository developed in the context of the EU-funded OpenAIRE program.

This project has been conceived and developed in the context of the María de Maetzu programme.*

1.2 Objectives

This work is intended to develop an application that allows semantic indexing, discourse classification and discovery of scientific publications found in Zenodo. The application is meant to be a prototype of a useful and helpful tool to ease the learning and discovery experience of researchers, students and more.

However, the main focus in this project will be directed towards the extraction, management and analysis of information, whether from the publications themselves or from external resources.

Finally, a fundamental aim of this work is to gain experience and knowledge in the text mining and natural language processing fields along the process of developing this thesis.

1.3 Structure of the thesis

The rest of this document is structured in 4 chapters as follows:

First off, a theoretical framework is introduced at the beginning. In this part, the relevant concepts, techniques and tools employed throughout the project are covered and discussed.

*This work is supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness under the María de Maeztu Units of Excellence Programme (MDM-2015-0502)

Then, the *Methodology* chapter focuses on the process and approaches followed to accomplish the objectives established.

Next, a detailed description of the application developed is carried out, specifying its overall architecture and the features developed.

Finally, the many distinct parts developed, as well as the overall system and application are evaluated to judge the quality and performance of each component.

Chapter 2

State of the art

2.1 Natural Language Processing

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is an area of research within the computer science, information engineering and artificial intelligence fields. NLP is focused on developing appropriate tools and techniques to make computer systems understand, learn and manipulate language.

This well-known subfield arises from the fact that computers cannot understand the huge collection of unstructured data that language is. Language is a complex, personal, intentional and idiosyncratic system that humans have crafted and modified for centuries. Therefore, structuring language in a clear and concise manner is no trivial task.

In fact, NLP faces many difficulties. For instance, dealing with ambiguity: a word can have many different meanings, can be used in many ways and can be expressed to communicate something else. It also has to discern and detect words and sentences and be robust to imperfect data like typos, errors and non-grammatical expressions.

In order to tackle these issues, Natural Language Processing benefits from a wide range of areas from the study of linguistics. Some of them are grouped into different classes and discussed in the list below:

- **Syntax:** it refers to the arrangement of words in a sentence such that they make grammatical sense.
 - Lemmatization: it consists in reducing the various inflected forms of a word into a single form for easy analysis known as a lemma. For instance, the lemma of "processing" would be "process".
 - Morphological segmentation: it involves dividing words into individual units called morphemes and depends on the language of the text. A morpheme is not identical to a word, and the principal difference between the two is that a morpheme may or may not stand alone, whereas a word, by definition, is freestanding [2]. For example, the word "unbreakable" comprises three morphemes: *un-* (a bound morpheme signifying "not"), *-break-* (the root, a free morpheme), and *-able* (a free morpheme signifying "can be done").
 - Word / Sentence segmentation: it involves dividing a large piece of continuous text into separate words/sentences.
 - Part-Of-Speech (POS) tagging: given a sentence, it tries to identify the part of speech for each word. By way of explanation, it tags each word as being either a noun, verb, adjective,...etc in relation to the sentence it belongs to.
 - Parsing: it determines the grammatical analysis (or parse tree) of a given sentence. There are two primary types of parsing, *dependency parsing*, which focuses on identifying the relationships between words (subject, primary object, predicates...) and *constituency parsing*, which aims to extract a constituency-based parse tree that represents the syntactic structure of a sentence.
- **Semantics:** the extraction of the true meaning that is conveyed by a sentence.
 - Named entity recognition (NER): it involves determining the parts of a text that can be identified and categorized into groups like names of people or places.

- Word sense disambiguation: given that a word can have many meanings, word sense disambiguation consists in obtaining the real expressed meaning of a word based on the context manifested by the surrounding text.
 - Coreference resolution: given a chunk of text, it tries to determine which words refer to the same entity (a person, an object, an idea...). A common example is detecting that a personal pronoun and a name refer to the same person: "*Bill said he would come.*". It is an important step for a lot of higher level NLP tasks that involve natural language understanding.
 - Relationship extraction: it is the task of extracting semantic relationships among named entities. These extracted relationships usually occur between two or more entities of a certain type (e.g. person, organization, location) and fall into a number of semantic categories (e.g. married to, employed by, lives in).
- **Other:**
- Identification of the rhetorical role: determine the topic or context of communication where a portion of text belongs, i.e. approach, background, conclusion...
 - Automatic summarization: its aim is to automatically produce a shortened, coherent, readable and understandable version of a certain text that contains its major points.

2.2 Open Access Repositories

Following the definition set forth by the Budapest Open Access Initiative (2002), open access refers to literature that provides:

"free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical

barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself. The only constraint on reproduction and distribution, and the only role for copyright in this domain, should be to give authors control over the integrity of their work and the right to be properly acknowledged and cited." [3]

Therefore, an open access repository or open archive is a digital platform established to collect, disseminate and preserve scientific output and make them freely available. Depositing a free copy of one's own work in an open access repository is known as self-archiving. Its purpose is maximizing the accessibility, usage and citation impact of the author's publications. The term "green open access" is often used to refer to this type of publishing, distinguishing it from gold open access, where the journal or the institution itself makes the articles publicly available to the reader.

Repositories can be either linked to an institution or department like the Oxford University Research Archive or linked to a research field or subject, like arXiv (physics, mathematics, computer science...) or PubMed (health and medicine). It is necessary to also mention both hybrid open access repositories or journals, which offer free access to some of its publications and academic social networks that also have some open access documents like ResearchGate and Mendeley.

2.2.1 *Zenodo*

Zenodo is an interdisciplinary open data repository service founded and maintained by CERN and developed under the European OpenAIRE program. Launched in May 2013, it has collected an enormous amount of data by offering researchers a place to deposit anything related to their research projects: reports, articles, software, datasets...

Zenodo has limited search to some basic facets like format, type or author assigned keywords and the documents' contents are not semantically indexed. Hence, the initiative to apply the text mining and natural language processing tools to extract valuable information from Zenodo's collection of publications was really attractive.

It allows semantic classification of the regions in a document, which can contribute to make them more easily discovered and retrieved.

2.3 Document Structure Analysis

When extracting relevant and meaningful data as text from a scientific publication, there is a clear first obstacle being faced: the publication is in image format, most commonly, in PDF. Despite the many XML dialects and scientific publishing technologies proposed during the last few years, PDF still constitutes the most widespread distribution format of scientific publications. This is due to the reliable format across many platforms that PDF offers, the ability to display high-resolution images within the document, the ease of storage, among many other reasons.

PDF is a layout-based data format for professional document rendering. Consequently, computers treat PDFs like images and not like text as we would wish, forcing the application of text extraction techniques. However, extracting the publication as plain text is not sufficient for our purposes. A structured version of the contents of the scientific publication is what we are aiming for. Therefore, customized approaches are necessary tools for the correct indexing of the scientific papers.

Document structure analysis, also called document layout analysis consists in identifying and classifying the various relevant sections in an image version of a text document. A human reader uses a variety of additional cues such as context, conventions and information about language, along with a complex reasoning process to decipher the contents of a document. An automatic system lacks these kinds of considerations and therefore it becomes an extremely difficult task [4].

The performance of any document structure analysis approach is obviously dependant on the quality of the extraction of the textual contents from the original PDF file. The extraction technique must be robust to different document layouts due to the own style and arrangement that every journal or publisher may have. Furthermore, it also has to take into account the wide range of structural elements of

scientific articles, since some may have sections or key structural elements that other publications lack.

Knowing the type of document that will be analyzed beforehand is important for an accurate categorization of the regions of interest within the document. Therefore, the conversion from image to structured text will be conditioned by the nature of the document. In this case, we are going to distinguish between general-purpose pdf-to-text conversion and pdf-to-text conversion for the special case of scientific publications. The former aims to convert to textual contents without any specific assumption on the type or contents of the document under analysis. These are some of the most well-known general-purpose PDF-to-text applications:

- **pdf2xml [5]:** it converts information contained in a PDF file into XML. Programmed in C++ and based on the Xpdf library.
- **Poppler [6]:** PDF rendering library based on the xpdf-3.0 code base. It is open source and programmed in C++
- **PDFbox [7]:** open source Java tool for working with PDF documents. It allows creation, manipulation and the ability to extract content from documents.
- **pdf2htmlEX [8]:** open source project of layout-preserving PDF to HTML converter. It is mainly coded in C++ and is based on Poppler to process the PDF files.

2.3.1 *PDF-to-text conversion for scientific publications*

The process of extracting rich textual information from a general PDF has been covered. However, a distinction needs to be made when dealing with scientific articles. These documents tend to include elements unique to their type like titles, authors and their affiliations, an abstract, section headings, tables, figures, formulas and many more.

PDF-to-text conversion oriented towards scientific publications demands the integration of a general-purpose converter whose output will be processed accordingly. Therefore, the system must implement customized approaches to identify structural elements specific for scientific publications. Some examples of tools with such functionalities are:

- **PDFX [9]**: online web service that parses PDF files of scientific publications by applying several heuristics related to the layout and the lexical features of a paper to identify its structural elements.
- **Cermine [10]**: Java open source library that processes the contents of PDF articles and properly classifies text zones as belonging to four general classes: metadata, references, body and other. The zone classifiers used by Cermine are Support Vector Machines that rely on lexical, geometrical, sequential and formatting features of the different zones of a paper to classify.
- **GROBID [11]**: Java open source library that exploits a chain of Conditional Random Field (a statistical modeling method) classifiers to extract a hierarchical set of structural elements from PDF papers.
- **SectLabel [12]**: open source library that uses a sequence tagging model (Conditional Random Fields) to associate to each sentence of a scientific paper a structural and rhetorical category chosen among a set of 23 structural categories (title, figure, section header, etc.) and 13 rhetorical categories (abstract, introduction, background, etc.)
- **PDFdigest [13]**: it deals with both text-based and image-based PDF articles using custom rule-based algorithms implemented with existing state-of-the-art open-source tools for both PDF-to-HTML conversion and image-based PDF Optical Character Recognition.

2.4 Scientific Discourse Characterization

Scientific discourse characterization aims to classify the concepts and ideas presented in a scientific article into clear groups. This characterization allows an easy interpretation of how the information is structured and discussed, a contextualized perspective of the contents and it supports tasks like the extraction of targeted information and summarization.

Generally, to characterize the rhetorical classes found within a scientific paper, a notation schema is defined and the contents are classified following an annotation procedure. The two main approaches most commonly known are:

- *Rhetorical Structure Theory*: it states that text is organized by a set of rhetorical relations that link minimal units of text to each other, forming a tree-like structure, where the most relevant units are placed on the top [14].
- *Zone Analysis*: it claims that text can be divided into zones by the global rhetorical status of each sentence. This approach is the most common.

A well-known type of Zone Analysis is *Argumentative Zoning*. Argumentative Zoning characterizes the ownership of the knowledge claims presented in the paper, thus identifying and motivating the new contributions of the author [15].

2.5 Citation Analysis

A citation is a mention to a published or unpublished source. It acknowledges the relevance of the works of others to the topic of discussion at the spot where the citation appears. The reasons behind the use of citations are numerous and they denote its importance:

- to give credit to the original author and use their work without plagiarizing
- it solidifies the arguments presented and provides facts

- it allows the reader to evaluate whether the referenced material supports the author's arguments
- help anyone who wants to discover further research about the contents and where it came from
- denotes the amount of research carried out

Despite being manifested in many different ways, citations can be considered as a link or a relation between a citing paper and a cited paper. The text of the **citing paper** surrounding the **inline citation*** is referred as the **citation context**. The piece of text from the *cited paper* that discusses the actual contents cited by the **citing paper** is often called *cited span*.

By establishing these links between papers, a network of citations can be formed. In fact, we can derive many different networks from these associations depending on the grouping performed. Here are some of the possible resulting networks:

- ***Citation network***: collection of links formed by connecting citing and cited papers.
- ***Bibliographic coupling network***: this network is characterized by the connection of papers that cite the same documents. These networks are especially useful to map similar research topics.
- ***Co-citation network***: in this case, the network relates papers that are cited by the same publications.
- ***Author bibliographic coupling networks***: similar to the bibliographic coupling networks, these relations connect authors that cite the same paper(s). They are often used to map the research activities of the authors.
- ***Author co-citation networks***: similar to the co-citation networks, in this case the connections are made between authors that are cited together in

*Marker made within a body of text to associate a reference with the contents of the surrounding text.

Figure 1: The elements in citing and cited papers

papers. Author co-citation networks are greatly useful to map intellectual influences on a certain field.

Both the network of citations and the textual contents of citation contexts are exploited in many different tasks including: research collaboration analysis, topic analysis and evolution, citation recommendation, scientific document summarization. Furthermore, a citation recommendation system can complement pure scientific literature search engines in helping to cope with the scientific information overload mentioned previously.

2.6 Dr. Inventor Text Mining Framework

The Dr. Inventor Text Mining Framework is a self-contained java library that enables the automated analysis of scientific publications. Each component of the framework is structured as a GATE[†] Processing Resource.

Given a paper (either in PDF or XML format), a set of Java methods and classes enables the access to the results of the analyses performed by Dr Inventor. It supports the characterization of several aspects of scientific publications including the identification of their structural elements, the enrichment of their bibliographic entries by accessing external on-line services, the rhetorical characterization of sentences, named entity linking and disambiguation and the automatic creation of summaries [16].

Figure 2: Diagram of the pipeline of Dr. Inventor.

[†]General Architecture for Text Engineering (GATE) is a Java suite of tools developed for many natural language processing tasks.

2.6.1 *PDF-to-text conversion*

This part of the framework is dedicated to the conversion of a PDF paper to a semistructured text by spotting basic structural elements (title, abstract, sections, bibliographic entries, etc.), so as to enable further processing. As section 2.3 discusses there are several tools that support this conversion but they can be divided into two main groups: general-purpose PDF-to-text converters and PDF-to-text converters for scientific publications.

For the purpose of the Dr. Inventor Framework, the obvious choice is a converter from the latter group. After a comparative test of these tools, in the first version of the Dr. Inventor Framework, the online Web API of PDFX was the system chosen. PDFX, thanks to its robust rule-based PDF analysis engine, manages to perform most of the times clean and consistent extractions of semi-structured textual contents from PDF files. In addition, it also spots the basic structural elements of a publication (title, abstract, sections, bibliographic entries, etc.).

Nonetheless, PDFX has two prominent restrictions. Firstly, it must not be overlooked that it is only available as a web service, which limits the efficiency. Secondly, the service allows files whose size will not surpass the 5 MB limit, which prevents the conversion of large PDF documents.

As a consequence, in future releases the framework allowed the user to decide whether to use PDFX or GROBID (which is not a web service) for the PDF-to-text conversion.

2.6.2 *Sentence splitter*

Once all the text contained in the document that has been extracted from the PDF, it is time to break the contents up in chunks of information, i.e. sentences. The sentence splitter's job is to spot sentences within a text and then separate each one for further analysis later on. To achieve this, the splitter identifies sentence boundaries, most commonly dots. However, it has to take into account that dots

do not represent sentence endings, they are also used for abbreviations, special notations, etc.

In order to isolate each individual sentence from the entire text, Dr Inventor uses a customized version of the rule-based sentence splitter integrated in ANNIE*. The authors of Dr. Inventor analyzed the sentence split errors performed on a set of 40 Computer Graphics papers (occurring with expressions like: i.e., et al., Fig., Tab.) and modified the sentence splitting rules of ANNIE in order to correctly deal with these situations [16].

2.6.3 *Inline citation spotter*

The identification and relation of inline citations inside the sentences is a task of great relevance in order to have a clear understanding of the concepts expressed in a scientific article and how they are related. The objective of the inline-citation spotter is fulfilling this task, and it is divided in the following steps:

Figure 3: Inline citation markers and spans.

- **Step A:** identification of inline citation spans and markers (shown in Fig. 3) in the textual contents of the paper by means of a set of rules implemented in JAPE, a pattern matching formalism available in GATE tailored to match different inline citation styles.

*A Nearly-New Information Extraction (ANNIE) is the information extraction system used by GATE. It relies on finite state algorithms and the JAPE (Java Annotation Patterns Engine) language.

- **Step B:** identification of the bibliographic entries, usually listed at the end of the paper.
- **Step C:** relate each inline citation marker to the referenced bibliographic entry by means of a set of heuristics.
- **Step D:** determine whether the citation has a syntactic role or not. For instance, if it has a syntactic role, the sentence loses meaning when the citation disappears and otherwise, it does not. This step is vital to support the dependency parsing performed later.

2.6.4 Web-based reference parser

Despite the presence of standards and protocols, bibliographic entries are often composed in many different ways depending on the article, the author and the journal. As a consequence, the information like the author, the title, the publication date, etc. is all piled up and mixed within a reference, hoping to be identified individually by the human reader.

Figure 4: Components in a reference.

It is extremely valuable to possess detailed and classified information about a bibliographic entry referenced by a document automatically. For instance, it enables the formation of the citation networks explained in section 2.5. Therefore, we aim to use a mechanism that given a reference, automatically identifies and stores each component.

Currently, there are many tools that allow the automatic identification of these elements. However, Dr Inventor employs these three web-based reference parsers:

- *FreeCite* [17] : on-line tool that analyzes citations by relying on a conditional random field sequence tagger trained on the CORA dataset [18], made of 1838 manually tagged bibliographic entries.
- *CrossRef* [19]: this Web service matches free form citations/bibliographic entries to the items of CrossRef publications metadata archive.
- *Bibsonomy* [20] : its Web API enables the retrieval of the BibTeX metadata of a publication from the Bibsonomy database by providing its title in the query.

Once the results from these three Web services are obtained, the system tries to decide the final title, list of authors, the year of publication and the journal of the publication by merging the outputs.

2.6.5 Citation-aware dependency parser

The citation-aware dependency parser attempts to determine the syntactic structure of the sentences of the paper. In order to achieve this, Dr. Inventor relies on the MATE dependency parser[†][21]. MATE analyzes each sentence in the paper by performing the following tasks: tokenization, lemmatization, POS tagging and dependency parsing.

In spite of that, the MATE dependency parser employed in Dr. Inventor is customized in such a way that it will take into account those inline citations that carry a syntactic role in the sentence, as mentioned previously. On the contrary, if the inline-citation spotter determines that a citation does not contribute any syntactic role to the sentence, the parser excludes it.

[†]Mate tools is a toolkit of statistical NLP tools comprising a lemmatizer, part-of-speech tagger, morphological tagger, dependency parser, and semantic role labeler.

2.6.6 *Scientific discourse/rhetorical annotator*

The scientific discourse annotator constitutes an essential stage of the Dr. Inventor pipeline. Given a sentence, the annotator has to automatically decide whether it belongs to one of the rhetorical classes established (Background, Challenge, Approach and Outcome) or to none. This task is accomplished by training a classification model.

The classifier was trained over the set of 8877 sentences belonging to 40 Computer Graphics papers that constitute the Dr. Inventor Rhetorically Annotated Corpus [22]. All the sentences of the Corpus have been manually characterized by three annotators by associating a scientific discourse category, obtaining a value of inter-annotator agreement [‡] (Cohen's k) equal to 0.6567.

The set of scientific rhetorical categories was established relying on the scientific discourse annotation arrangement proposed by [23, 24]. It is significant to manifest that this particular set of categories has been selected with the sole purpose of correctly characterizing the contents of Computer Graphics papers.

The sentence classifier integrated in the Framework benefits from the help of the lexical and syntactic properties of the sentence as features. This classifier is based on a Support Vector Machine with a linear kernel. The machine learning Java library Weka was exploited in order to carry out all the tasks mentioned.

The result obtained by this classifier is a F1 score equal to 0.764 as result of a 10-fold cross validation over the set of sentences of the Dr. Inventor Rhetorically Annotated Corpus.

2.6.7 *Knowledge graph builder*

The last stage of the entire Dr. Inventor pipeline is responsible of building a graph-based representation of the contents of the papers and its relations. The knowledge graph builder has a set of rules implemented that extract subject-verb-object triples

[‡]Cohen's kappa, ranging from 0 (no agreement) to 1 (complete agreement), measures the agreement between two raters who each classify N items into C mutually exclusive categories.

from the output of the citation-aware dependency parser. These triples are merged to create a graph that links and simplifies the concepts with each other (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Diagram showing the difference between the dependency parsing tree and the knowledge graph.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter's intention is to cover the process and methodology followed to achieve the objectives established. Particularly, it will be focused on the architecture of the proposed system that extracts, manipulates and indexes data from Zenodo. In addition, the details and nuances regarding the data received will also be addressed.

3.1 The proposed system

A general picture of the system architecture is depicted in Figure 6. It consists of several tools that are either designed for this project (like *references.py*, *downloadEntries.py* and *labelHTML.py*) or re-used from projects of other authors and developers (like Dr. Inventor and pdf2htmlEX). This diagram also displays the items or files that are being manipulated throughout the pipeline and the final destinations of the outputs, shown in a grey and light blue box, respectively. The input to the system is a massive JSON file containing all the entries in Zenodo, from which we will only select the entries that fulfill a certain criteria. This is going to be further discussed in section 3.2.

For every selected entry, the system attempts to parse its references and find their corresponding URLs in an online repository using *references.py*. Next up, it downloads the PDF file of the document.

Figure 6: Simplified diagram of the data pipeline

Once the PDF file is obtained, we enter the second stage of the system. Here, the PDF file is injected into the respective pipelines and processes of the Dr. Inventor and pdf2htmlEX tools.

The Dr. Inventor engine is responsible for automatically identify and extract rich information from the document, like the structural elements, the relations between inline citations and the references, the discursive sections within the article, etc. However, the pdf2htmlEX algorithm converts the PDF file into an accurate representation of the document in the HTML format. This conversion is applied in order to be able to display the article in our web application in a structured text format.

Now that we have both the original data from Zenodo and the extracted data provided by Dr. Inventor, we can merge these two files into a single output JSON file and upload it to our ElasticSearch index.

Finally, the contents from the extracted JSON have to be merged and matched into

the HTML representation of the article using the *labelHTML.py* code. This process is addressed in more detail in section 3.6. Once the final HTML file is attained, the system uploads it to the server where our application will be hosted.

3.2 The input data

In order to obtain the structured data found in Zenodo until then, we contacted the staff working at Zenodo. They provided a massive JSON file whose size surpassed 1.8 GB and contained nearly 500.000 entries in total.

The received file contained a wide range of information regarding each entry. Some of the most relevant fields within each entry are mentioned here:

- File-related fields: like the name of the file, its format type, and the size in bytes.
- URLs: various relevant links that lead to the original post of the entry in Zenodo, to the bucket where it is stored and more.
- ID: the internal identification key that Zenodo employs to distinguish between entries. Since this field is certainly useful it has also been exploited in our system to identify entries.
- Resource type: the category or class where the entry belongs to, like: journal article, conference paper, book section, dataset, photo, diagram and many more.
- DOI (Digital Object Identifier): a persistent identifier used to identify objects uniquely across the internet, standardized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO).
- Dates: numerous dates of meaningful events regarding the management of the entries in Zenodo. For instance, the date of creation/upload of the post or the date of update.

- *Metadata*: all sorts of essential information about the actual document like: title, authors, keywords, publication date, journal, language and many more.

In order to get a good grasp of the data obtained, the entries were classified based on a field mentioned above: *resource type*. Out of a total of 494.232 entries, they are categorized in the following way:

Resource type	Num. of entries	Resource type	Num. of entries
Figure	194.152	Drawing	1.965
Journal Article	154.027	Book section	1.880
Software	45.470	Working Paper [†]	1.259
Dataset	35.415	Video/Audio	964
Conference Paper	30.208	Preprint**	921
Presentation	5.952	Lesson	728
Report	4.190	Technical Note	441
Other [†]	4.158	Software doc.	163
Poster	2.911	Proposal	135
Photo	2.662	Project milestone	71
Book	2.266	Diagram	53
Thesis	2.084	Plot	44
Project Deliverable	2.077	Patent	36

Table 1: Categorization of the entries based on the resource types.

† : refers to databases, studies, surveys, blog notes, case studies...

‡ : drafts of papers.

** : a version of a scholarly or scientific paper that precedes formal peer review and publication in a peer-reviewed scholarly or scientific journal.

|| : a proposal of a project.

3.3 Pre-processing

3.3.1 Entry selection

Once a clear perspective of the input data was reached, it was time to select and download the entries that will be manipulated. Since this project is intended to be a small prototype or a simple demo of what could be made by extracting and connecting all the data from all the entries of Zenodo, we must filter most of the

entries and select a collection of them that are meaningful for our purpose. There is an obvious first screening, dismiss all the entries that are not documents: software, datasets, figures, photos, videos, diagrams, etc.

Furthermore, given that we are interested in traditional scientific research documents, we can get rid of entries like: book sections, lessons, presentations, proposals, etc. This narrows our list to our two main categories colored in blue in Table 1: journal article and conference paper. These two categories are the most relevant for our objective and there are plenty of entries in them.

While going through the narrowed list, it is easy to notice that many of the articles and conference papers are not written in English. A reasonable approach to shrink the size of the current list would be to select those entries written in this language. The "language" field within the metadata section of the original JSON file comes in very handy to accomplish this task. However, this field was not present in most of the entries. An automatic language detection approach was considered, but it was dismissed because it was not necessary. The list is reduced to 43.033 articles and conference papers employing the "language" field.

The number of topics and research areas within Zenodo are really broad: agriculture, computer science, economics, biology, zoology... Since one of the main purposes of this project is to facilitate the discovery of connections and relations between articles and topics, it would be of significant relevance to target entries that belong to a certain field of research. We addressed this by establishing a collection of related keywords, and selecting those entries that had any of these keywords. Consequently, the number of occurrences for each keyword were computed, shown in Figure 7.

The collection of keywords selected was decided to be related mainly to the computer science field, since it feels close to home. It is meaningful to take into account that the selected entries may also belong to other research areas, since the keywords are broad enough. Figure 7 shows the 11 selected keywords (in descending order of number of occurrences): *optimization*, *data mining*, *modeling*, *neural networks*, *classification*, *neural network*, *clustering*, *innovation* and *image processing*.

Figure 7: Number of occurrences for the top 50 keywords

Therefore, the resulting number of articles and conference papers that contain any of these keywords is 1119. Nevertheless, for practical reasons and to ease the development process, we got rid of approximately three quarters of these entries and we were left with a final list of around 270 entries.

3.3.2 Reference parsing

As discussed in section 2.6.4, Dr. Inventor can parse the references identified using an external reference parser. If we decided to use this feature, it would mean that the possible errors that Dr. Inventor may have produced while extracting the references would be inserted into this section of the pipeline.

Fortunately, our input data from Zenodo provides the references in each article, which helps us get rid of those possible flaws and is advantageous for a higher quality parsing. In addition, this will help Dr. Inventor to execute faster, since the reference parsing option in Dr. Inventor is notoriously time consuming. As a consequence, the references are parsed before entering the Dr. Inventor stage.

The "references" field is an array of strings, and each string contains a reference

arranged in order of appearance in the article. However, it has a minor flaw: the array always contains 8 strings or fewer. If the entry contains more than 8 references, it divides the first 7 in different strings and piles all the rest in the eighth string. This must be due to the storing convention that Zenodo has, probably for consistency.

Regardless, the code responsible for this task takes this fact into account and divides the grouped references by identifying the initial brackets ("`[<number of reference>`") that they all must contain.

Next up, the code performs an API request using the `cURL` command tool to the reference parser which, in our case is `FreeCite`. This tool accepts many references to parse in a single request by appending "`&citation[]="`" before every reference.

Then, `FreeCite` returns a XML file with his attempt to identify these items: *authors*, *title*, *journal*, *volume of the journal*, *number of the journal*, *pages* and *year of publication*. If the parser was unable to classify any of these elements it returns an empty string as the result of that element. Once the results are obtained, the code injects them into the JSON file as a field called: "`parsed_references`".

3.3.3 Reference DOI and URL seeking

An attractive opportunity is brought up now that our references are parsed. The acquirement of more information related about each reference now becomes less complex. We can take advantage of this fact by seeking highly significant data about each reference, like the DOI and the URLs that lead to the entire publication elsewhere.

From a final application standpoint, this will allow the user of the application to visit, read and examine the referenced paper instantaneously. Therefore boosting the overall purposes of citations explained in section 2.5.

Well-known repositories and academic social network provide RESTful APIs that could be appropriate for this purpose. `Bibsonomy`, `Mendeley`, `Springer` and `ScienceDirect` are the main services that were taken into account.

After analyzing most of the results provided by the reference parser, it was concluded that a wide majority of the references had at least the title and the authors correctly parsed. Plus, most of the APIs mentioned before allow to perform both queries based on variables like author, title and year of publication and queries based on a free text query. Accordingly, the queries attempted were based on free text queries containing the title and authors and by querying exclusively the title and the authors individually.

Eventually, after trying these combinations with these APIs, the Mendeley and Bibsonomy API turned out to deliver the most accurate results.

However, a reliable procedure was needed to decide whether the returned results were the ones expected or not. Here's a simple pseudo-code explanation of how the results were selected:

```
for every reference:
```

- if it has authors: query based on authors
- if it has title:
 - query based on title
 - free text query containing the title
- if the three queries have one result in common: select result
- if the general query contains a single result: select result
- if the free text and title query have the same result: select result

```
write selection to json file
```

3.4 Dr. Inventor

This section describes the features of the Dr. Inventor framework that have been employed for this particular project. Furthermore, some details and technicalities that emerge when Dr. Inventor is used in practice are going to be discussed too.

The framework requires a text configuration file containing some constants and paths defined. In particular, it must contain the path to the resource folder that contains all the tools used by Dr. Inventor, and the user API keys of Bibsonomy and BabelNet (if they are used). Then, a collection of files is created, containing all the file objects of the documents about to be processed, which in our case are all pdf files.

Among the many features that Dr. Inventor provides, some of them are not be required for our purposes like the parsing of bibliographic entries (as mentioned in section 3.3.2) and the creation of the knowledge graph. Dr. Inventor enables us to disallow these functionalities from the system. Taking this adjustments into account, we can start processing the documents following the Dr. Inventor pipeline shown in Figure 2.

For each paper, the code converts the PDF file into a `drInventorDocument` object through the `parsePDF()` function. This `drInventorDocument` object is processed through these stages of the pipeline: *the sentence splitter*, *the inline citation spotter*, *the citation-aware dependency parser* and *the scientific discourse annotator*.

As a result, a JSON file representing all the extracted data is received as the output. The original JSON file that contains the information about that entry provided by Zenodo is inserted into this output file obtained after the process. Therefore, we possess all the information, both original and extracted in a single JSON file.

Finally, once the output of this section is obtained, it is uploaded to Elasticsearch[†] so that its contents can be later accessed from the application.

3.5 PDF-to-HTML conversion

This section is going to be focused on how the transformation of the PDF document to its HTML representation was approached. This approach is essentially based off of the pdf2htmlEX mechanism.

[†]a distributed, RESTful search and analytics engine with an HTTP web interface and schema-free JSON documents.

pdf2htmlEX renders PDF files in HTML, utilizing modern Web technologies, aims to provide an accuracy rendering, while keeping optimized for Web display. Text, fonts and formats are natively preserved in HTML, math formulas, figures and images are also supported [8]. pdf2htmlEX was created by Lu Wang back in 2013 due to the lack of handy tools to present PDF documents online.

PDF and HTML are quite different formats. The PDF format focuses on the capability of accurate representing and printing all kinds of documents. HTML focus on multimedia, user interaction, network optimization. Here lies the main reason for converting to HTML. It allows interaction with the actual document (for example the possibility to highlight the classes identified by Dr. Inventor and inspect them) and offer a more reliable format for the web.

Plus, pdf2htmlEX was first specifically designed for scientific papers, which often contain different fonts and complicated formulas and figures, making it an excellent tool for our project.

For every PDF file downloaded, the pdf2htmlEX program is called from the command line and the resulting HTML file is stored in a different folder. In addition, the program allows some argument inputs. In our case we applied a 1.35 zoom as an argument since the default output displayed was too tiny.

3.6 HTML Labeling

The HTML labeling stage is one of the last in the system pipeline and probably the most difficult. Its existence is directly conditioned by the following issue: although we have the analyzed and categorized contents of the paper in the JSON file outputted in the Dr. Inventor stage, we do not know their location in the HTML representation. This problem disallows user interaction with for instance, a selected rhetorical class or the references. Therefore, this stage is responsible for matching each sentence extracted with its corresponding representation in the HTML file.

First off, an extensive analysis of how each HTML file was structured was carried out in order to be able to process the information contained properly. pdf2htmlEX

outputs the HTML files in such a way that each page is a `<div>` tag with a `pf` class and each line of the text contents of the documents is contained in a `<div>` tag too. The HTML files were parsed with the help of BeautifulSoup[‡].

By the nature of text, each line in the original document may contain parts of more than one sentence. As a consequence, most `<div>` tags representing a line in the HTML file will contain parts of more than one sentence. This essentially means that `<div> ≠ sentence` (Fig. 8).

In order to solve this complication a rearrangement of `<div>` tags was attempted so that each tag contained a single sentence. It was unsuccessful due to the complicated structure that the HTML file has, in order to be a perfect copy of the PDF file. This rearrangement transformed the HTML file into a complete mess with no intelligible content.

Figure 8: Difference between the `<div>` tag and a sentence.

The arrangement in the HTML file caused another problem. For proper display purposes, sometimes `<div>` tags contained single letters or very few characters, complicating the task even more. Those tags containing text whose length is shorter or equal to 25 are discarded.

3.6.1 Algorithm

First of all, the JSON file is read and all the sentences and references of the article are stored. Then, each page and line tag in the file is given a unique ID for structural

[‡]a famous Python library for pulling and parsing data out of HTML and XML files.

and easy access purposes. Furthermore, the text contained in each `<div>` tag is stored in a Python dictionary with the `<div>` tag ID as its key.

Now, given a sentence we look for its matching tag by iterating over the dictionary mentioned above. For each tag we perform a set of screenings based on their length to reject unwanted candidates. If a tag candidate fulfills the requirements, the code checks whether they appear in the sentence literally or not. This first assessment is very valuable due to the fact that it allows to decide soon enough whether the candidate is correct or not with extreme accuracy.

In case they do, that tag is labeled as belonging to that sentence. Since in most cases they do not appear literally, the code performs a set of detailed operations to determine if it belongs to the class or not. They are the following:

1. **Compute the edit distance****: using the NLTK^{††} python library we obtain how dissimilar the text from the tag and the sentence are.
2. **Compute ratio of difference**: the edit distance does not take into account the difference in length of the two strings. If we subtract the difference in length from the edit distance, we will obtain the number of modifications without counting the addition of the extra characters. This allows us to compute how different these strings are:

$$ratio = \frac{edit_distance - (length_sentence - length_tag)}{length_tag}$$

3. **Compute consecutive ratio**: in case the ratio of difference accounts for 50% or less (which means that its difference represents less than half the sentence) the code counts the number of consecutive tokens in the text of the tag that are contained in the sentence. This allows us to compute how similar these strings are:

**measure to quantify how dissimilar two strings are to one another by counting the number of operations required to transform one string into the other.

^{††}Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) is a suite of libraries and programs for symbolic and statistical natural language processing for English written in the Python programming language.

$$ratio = \frac{number_consecutive_tokens}{length_tag}$$

In case the ratio of consecutive tokens is larger or equal than 50%, the tag is marked as valid to belong to that sentence.

For efficiency and accuracy purposes, if the algorithm detects at any time that at least 80% of the sentence has been already found or that a 20% or less of the sentence is left to be found, it breaks the loop and proceeds to search for the next sentence. Furthermore, the code also takes advantage of the fact that the tags and the sentences often follow the same order. Therefore, if a part of a sentence is found in a certain page, the algorithm will only search for the remaining part in that page exclusively.

In addition, in case that a sentence has one or more tags labeled as belonging to it the algorithm checks if there are any unlabeled tags between these two and it automatically marks them as valid. This is especially useful for labeling tags that were discarded in the initial screenings.

Finally, once all the HTML files have been labeled, they are uploaded to the server, where they will be requested by the application.

Pseudocode:

```
for each sentence/ref in the json:
```

- for each text in each div:
 - if the length(text) > 25:
 - > if length(text) <= length(sentence):
 - if value appears explicitly in the sentence:
 - -> remove from dictionary
 - -> label tag
 - else:

- -> compute edit distance
- -> compute ratio of difference
- -> if ratio of difference ≤ 0.5 :
 - ———> compute consecutive ratio
 - ———> if consecutive ratio ≤ 0.5 :
 - ———> remove from dictionary
 - ———> label tag

Chapter 4

The Web Application

This chapter describes the web application module designed for this thesis. An overview of the entire architecture of the application will be addressed first, presenting its components and then each section will be defined in further detail. This application can be found in: <http://scientmin.taln.upf.edu/zenodo/>

4.1 Overview

The application is structured in the following fashion. Firstly, at the core a collection of web pages are linked with each other forming the user interface. The application is divided in three main sections designed to offer different services: the search section, the explore section and the statistics section. These sections will be further discussed in their respective segment. A detailed representation of the architecture of the application is displayed in Figure 9.

The starting point of the application is the `index.html` page, which provides a general menu of the application. From this page, the user can navigate to any of the offered sections.

The *search* section allows two distinct forms of search: general and faceted search. Depending on the queries performed the application displays a set of results related to the query. After selecting a result, the `article.html` page is displayed, with the

labeled HTML representation of the document embedded in it.

The *explore* section is able to show graphs that display the connections between either keywords and articles or keywords and authors. Its purpose is to boost the discovery and understanding of the relationships between these items. Finally, the *statistics* section offers a graphic representation of the data indexed in Elasticsearch.

Figure 9: Architecture of the web application.

The contents of each page are manipulated by making use of the capabilities of Javascript and its powerful library jQuery. In some cases, these tools are also applied to request certain information to Elasticsearch, the server and Kibana*, as we will explain later in each circumstance. The design of every web page in the application is carried out by CSS and a certain collection of Bootstrap[†] elements.

4.2 Search

The search section is designed to offer a reliable method to find the article the user is looking for or to research about a certain topic or concept. This fact caused the distinction between the two approaches implemented to search the articles: the general search and the faceted or specific search.

*open source data visualization plugin for Elasticsearch. It provides visualization capabilities on top of the content indexed on an Elasticsearch cluster.

[†]open source toolkit for developing with HTML, CSS, and JS.

The image shows a search interface with two main sections. The top section is titled 'General Search' and contains a single text input field with the placeholder text 'Search' and a blue 'Search' button to its right. The bottom section is titled 'Specific Search' and contains several filter options, each with a grey header and a white input field: 'Filter by Keyword' with 'Keyword' in the field; 'Filter by word in Title' with 'Word in Title' in the field; 'Filter by Author' with 'Author' in the field; and 'Filter by Years' with 'From' and 'To' labels, each followed by a 'Year' dropdown menu. Below these filters is a grey 'Reset filters' button and a large blue 'Search' button.

Figure 10: Snapshot of the search section.

After any search has been carried out, the application displays a list containing all the results provided by Elasticsearch. Each result is represented in a box containing the most relevant information about the result, like the title, the authors, the keywords, the year of publication and a piece of the abstract (as shown in Fig. 11).

4.2.1 *General Search*

Similarly to most search engines, in the general search section the user can type any free text query. the application will show all the publications in which this query matches any parameter.

When the user performs a general search query, the application reads the input free text query and it produces a request to Elasticsearch through a client. The request demands Elasticsearch by using a multi match query to return all articles in which the query appears in any of these fields: *keywords*, *title*, *authors*, *abstract*, *publication year*, *references* and the plain text.

However, some of these fields are more relevant than others, therefore they are given

The screenshot shows a search interface with the following elements:

- Search Filters:** Keyword (machine), Title (Word in Title), Author (Author), Filter by Years (From Year To Year).
- Buttons:** Reset filters, Search.
- Results:** 9 results.

The first three results are:

- Classification of Political Affiliations by Reduced Number of Features** (2015)
 Vesile Evrim, Aliyu Awwal
 Abstract: By the evolvement in technology, the way of expressing opinions switched direction to the digital world. The domain of politics, as one of the hottest topics of opinion mining research, merged together with the behavior analysis for affiliation determination in texts, which constitutes the subject of this paper. This study aims to classify the text in news/blogs either as Republican or Democrat with the minimum number of features. As an initial set, 68 features which 64 were constituted by Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC) features were tested against 14 benchmark classification algorithms. In the later experiments, the dimensions of the feature vector reduced based on the 7 feature selection algorithms. The results show that the "Decision Tree", "Rule Induction" and "M5 Rule" classifiers when used with "SVM" and "IGR" feature selection algorithms performed the best up to 82.5% ac...
 politics, machine learning, feature selection, liwc
- Hand Gesture Interpretation Using Sensing Glove Integrated with Machine Learning Algorithms** (2016)
 Aqsa Ali, Aleem Mushtaq, Attaullah Memon, Monna
 Abstract: In this paper, we present a low cost design for a smart glove that can perform sign language recognition to assist the speech impaired people. Specifically, we have designed and developed an Assistive Hand Gesture Interpreter that recognizes hand movements relevant to the American Sign Language (ASL) and translates them into text for display on a Thin-Film-Transistor Liquid Crystal Display (TFT LCD) screen as well as synthetic speech. Linear Bayes Classifiers and Multilayer Neural Networks have been used to classify 11 feature vectors obtained from the sensors on the glove into one of the 27 ASL alphabets and a predefined gesture for space. Three types of features are used; bending using six bend sensors, orientation in three dimensions using accelerometers and contacts at vital points using contact sensors. To gauge the performance of the presented design, the training dat...
 american sign language, assistive hand gesture interpreter, human-machine interface, machine learning, sensing glove
- Massive Lesions Classification using Features based on Morphological Lesion Differences** (2007)
 U. Bottigli, D. Cascio, F. Fauci, B. Golosio, R. Magro, G.L. Masala, P. Oliva, G. Raso, S. Stumbo
 Abstract: Purpose of this work is the development of an automatic classification system which could be useful for radiologists in the investigation of breast cancer. The software has been designed in the framework of the MAGIC-5 collaboration. In the automatic classification system the suspicious regions with high probability to include a lesion are extracted from the image as regions of interest (ROIs). Each ROI is characterized by some features based on morphological lesion differences. Some classifiers as a Feed Forward Neural Network, a K-Nearest Neighbours and a Support Vector Machine are used to distinguish the pathological records from the healthy ones. The results obtained in terms of sensitivity (percentage of pathological ROIs correctly classified) and specificity (percentage of non-pathological ROIs correctly classified) will be presented through the Receive Operating Characteristic cur...
 neural networks, k-nearest neighbours, supportvector machine, computer aided diagnosis

Figure 11: Snapshot of the results displayed after a search query.

what is known by Elasticsearch as a **boost**, which means that a result that matches the query in any of the boosted fields is given a higher priority. The results with the highest priority will be displayed at the top. These are the boosted fields: *publication year* (boost = 5), *keywords* (boost = 3), *title* (boost = 3) and *authors* (boost = 3).

4.2.2 Faceted Search

On the contrary, the faceted search section allows the user to search based on specific parameters that are usually relevant, like the title, authors, keywords and year. The application filters the publications that match each parameter inserted.

In the case of a faceted search query, the request to Elasticsearch is executed in a different fashion. By taking advantage of the **must** option that queries in Elasticsearch support, the application ensures that each and every of the restrictions suggested by the user for each facet are fulfilled. Therefore, if for instance, the user inputs a faceted query attempting to find articles with the keyword "*clustering*", the code sends a request to Elasticsearch that looks like this:

...

```
query: {  
  
  -> bool:{  
  
    —> must:[  
  
      ———> {match: {'zenodo.metadata.keywords': 'clustering'}}  
  
    —> ]  
  
  -> }  
  
}
```

...

4.3 Article display

When a publication result is selected, a page is shown displaying the publication and relevant information about it. like the title, the authors, the keywords, the year of publication and the DOI (Fig. 12).

A collection of switches is displayed in the bottom-left part of the page. These allow the user to highlight certain parts of the document like, the rhetorical classes (Background, Approach, Challenge and Outcome), the abstract, and the references (Fig. 12).

If the user clicks on a certain highlighted sentence, a sentence box appears, displaying the full sentence. If the selected sentence has an **inline citation** of a reference, the application highlights it, allowing the user to display the corresponding reference and its parsed components (Title, Authors, Journal, Year...) by clicking on it (Fig. 13).

The screenshot shows a Zenodo article page. On the left, there is a sidebar with filters for 'Rhetorical Classes' (Background, Challenge, Approach, Outcome) and 'Other Classes' (Abstract, References). The main content area displays the article title, authors (Aqsa Ali, Aleem Mushtaq, Attaullah Memon and Monna), and a brief abstract. The article text is visible in a smaller font, discussing a smart glove design for sign language recognition using machine learning and sensor technology.

Figure 12: Snapshot of an article being displayed.

Selected Item

"In EMG based approach, EMG sensors are used to sense the muscle activity [10]."

Reference #10

Muhammad Zahak Jamal, 'Signal Acquisition Using Surface EMG and Circuit Design Considerations for Robotic Prosthesis'.

DOI: 10.5772/52556 or Visit in Mendeley

Title	Signal Acquisition Using Surface EMG and Circuit Design Considerations for Robotic Prosthesis
Authors	Muhammad Zahak Jamal
Journal	Computational Intelligence in Electromyography Analysis - A Perspective on Current Applications and Future Challenges

Figure 13: Snapshot of a sentence that contains a highlighted citation and the reference with its parsed elements below.

4.4 Explore

The explore section enables the exhibition of graphs that represent the connections between either keywords and articles or keywords and authors. Its purpose is to

boost the discovery and understanding of the relationships between these items. These graphs are created using the *d3.js* Javascript library.

Figure 14: Snapshot of the Keyword & Article graph in the explore section.

As mentioned before, this section displays two different graphs. The first one is a graph that links keywords with the articles that use those keywords (Fig. 14). This graph is really interesting to map the relations between keywords and it could be greatly useful to identify categories and topics and how they are related. In addition, this graph allows the user to navigate and display any article that appears in the graph.

The other graph connects keywords and the authors that have mentioned them in their articles. In this case, this map of connections is useful to identify the topics and fields that a certain author is interested or invested in.

4.5 Statistics

Finally, the statistics section offers a meaningful graphic representation of the data indexed in Elasticsearch by exploiting the functionalities of Kibana. It consists of a dashboard containing 5 attractive plots, charts and other interesting visual representations of data:

1. **Stacked area plot of keywords:** given a time frame, which in this case is from 2007 to 2017, the plot shows the number of mentions that a certain keyword had every year represented in stacked areas.
2. **Histogram of keywords:** in the x-axis, each portion represents a keyword and the y-axis displays the number of occurrences that each keyword has.
3. **Publications per year:** this simple plot graphs the number of documents that have been published each year.
4. **Authors cloud:** in this visualization, the names of the authors are displayed with a size proportional to the number of articles published.
5. **Heat map of authors and keywords:** this heat map represents the connections displayed in the keyword and author graph in the explore section, but from a different perspective and exclusively for the authors with a highest number of publications.

Figure 15: Stacked area plot of keywords, Histogram of keywords and publications per year.

Figure 16: Authors cloud and heat map of authors and keywords.

Chapter 5

Evaluation

All figures mentioned in this chapter can be found in Appendix A.

5.1 Evaluation of the system

Once the entire application was functional, it was time to evaluate many different aspects of the system and the application. In order to test our project, an appropriate survey was designed and was handed to volunteers to be filled.

The number of volunteers ended up being 36. Among these volunteers were PhD students from the DTIC department, researchers from TALN, UPF students, and friends. Before beginning to fill in the survey, the users were given a brief explanation of how the application works and a few relevant concepts.

The survey focused on testing a set of important features that will be detailed here:

1. *Search engines*: the survey asked the volunteer to perform any search query desired in both the general and faceted search engines. There were query suggestions like keywords or common words (neural network, clustering, approach, model...) to ease the job. In addition, in the case of the faceted search, the surveyed had to perform two different search queries instead of one because it was considered to be more important due to the variety of facet restrictions

offered. After performing the search, the survey asked how related were the results obtained to the query. The answers can be observed in Figures 17 and 18.

We can conclude that the faceted search engine is more effective at delivering the requested content. However, this may be conditioned by the nature of the faceted way of searching. The general search turns out to have an insufficient performance, and it would need to be redefined to be more rigorous.

2. Rhetorical classes: even though we know that the Dr. Inventor classifier has a f1-score of 0.764, errors could have been committed when labeling the HTML and we also want to perceive how the user valued it. Therefore, the participants were asked to determine whether the highlighted sentences for each rhetorical class actually belonged to it or not. They also had to decide how they would rate this particular feature. The results are displayed in figure 19.

The answers align more less with the f1-score of the classifier, although the average seems to be substantially smaller.

3. Inline citations: we also wanted to know how well Dr. Inventor identified the inline citations in our particular project and if our system was highlighting them appropriately whenever a selected box showed a sentence containing an inline citation. Therefore the users were asked and the results are shown in figure 20.

As we can see, a wide majority of the inline citations appear to be identified and highlighted properly.

4. References: when it comes to the references a lot of issues had to be tested:
 - First off, the user was asked to use the reference switch button to locate the references. Then, the user had to tell if the references were highlighted properly or not in a scale from 0 to 10.

The answers shown in figure 21 conclude that most references were highlighted correctly, but a considerable amount of them were not found by the HTML labeler.

- Next up, the user had to select three random references and check if those selected appeared on the "selected item" box or not. This is tested in order to determine whether the reference selected in the HTML file is marked as the correct reference.

Figure 22 helps us determine that although a majority of the references were properly matched, a substantial amount were either not found or were mistakenly assigned.

- Then, the user is asked to evaluate for each of the three references how accurately were the individual elements of the reference identified by the reference parser.

As shown in figure 23, a substantial number of references do not have their items identified. This is probably due to the fact that a considerable amount of references are not found. However, those that are found appear to be parsed quite successfully.

- Finally, regarding the references, the volunteer was asked whether the DOI or external URL was displayed for that particular reference.

As shown in the results in figure 24, very few references contain a DOI or an external URL. This is further discussed and matches the results of section 5.3.

5. Explore and Statistics sections: these sections are not as dense as the search section, but an understanding of the performance of the Explore and Statistics sections is very valuable. The users were asked to rate both sections on a scale from 0 to 10. Furthermore, the survey also asked if the section was considered useful, to which all the users answered "Yes" for both sections.

The results shown in figure 25 portray a better performance from the Explore section, although they both have a similar average score. This is probably due to the higher usefulness provided by the explore section.

6. Overall application: lastly, the surveyed volunteer is asked to rank the overall application on a scale from 0 to 10 too.

The answers shown in 16 indicate that the general assessment of the application is positive, even though a considerable amount of volunteers consider it lacks quality and there is a lot of room left to improve.

At the end of the survey, suggestions and recommendations were allowed. Greatly valuable takes were suggested like the addition of more articles in the field of law, the improvement of the graphs in the explore section for quicker and better performance and a clear structure and identification of the elements in the statistics section.

5.2 Analysis of the HTML Labeling

The section 3.6.1 explains in extensive detail the algorithm adopted to locate and label the sentences in the HTML file. In order to quantify the quality and accuracy of this location task, the code contained a variable called `ratio_found` that stored, on a scale of 0 to 1, how much of the current sentence had been already found.

After labeling each HTML file representing a document, all the ratios were gathered to generate the plot shown in figure 27. For each possible ratio, it displays the number of sentences that have that ratio.

As we can see, the vast majority of sentences are close to high ratio values, which means that most of their contents were found. Nevertheless, a prominent amount of sentences have a ratio of 0, which means that they were not found.

This issue was found early on in the project and it conditioned the current design of the HTML algorithm deeply due to the amount of errors that the not found sentences cause later on in the system.

In Table 2, a collection of helpful indicators and measures are shown that reinforce our intuitions. As we can see, the percentage of not found sentences is substantially high at 11%, an 84% of the sentences have at least 50% of their contents labeled and more than half the sentences (60%) have at least 80% of their content labeled. In addition, the average and median of ratios are high enough to consider the algorithm as effective.

Total number of sentences	36.543	Percentage found	89%
Sentences found	32.366	Percentage not found	11%
Sentences not found	4.177	Percentage with ratio > 0.5	84%
Sentences with ratio > 0.5	30.772	Percentage with ratio > 0.8	60%
Sentences with ratio > 0.8	21.748	Average ratio	0.73
		Median of ratios	0.84
		Standard Dev. of the ratio	0.32

Table 2: Relevant data and percentages regarding the HTML labeling.

5.3 Analysis of the reference DOI and URL acquisition

As explained in section 3.3.3, in order to obtain the information from the Mendeley and Bibsonomy API, three different queries are made: a free text query containing the title, a faceted query for the authors and another one faceted for the title. An extensive analysis was carried out for 20 articles and all their respective references that added up to a total of 326. The results can be found in Tables 3 and 4.

The algorithm proposed in section 3.3.3 gives a remarkable precision due to how restrictive the algorithm is. However, the algorithm misses out on a lot of references present in Mendeley and Bibsonomy that are not detected (84 false negatives) which reduces the f1-score. Although, other approaches could be implemented to improve these results, the option that seems better for a larger number of references in our application with DOIs and external URLs is to search in the other APIs proposed.

Found by intersection	74
Found by general query	12
Found by general and title query	43
Found in Bibsonomy	23
Total found	152
Not found	174
Total number of references	326

Table 3: Results of the DOI & URL seeking.

Ratio of found references	0,47
True positives (correct matches)	142
False positives (incorrect matches)	10
False negatives	84
Precision	0,93
Recall	0,68
F1-score	0,79

Table 4: Computation of ratios and F1-score.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

According to the results presented in the previous chapter we can conclude that the developed system and application serve the purposes proposed. The application contains a reasonable amount of articles that can be either searched and/or discovered in a fairly effective manner. In addition, this prototype demonstrates that similar fully developed applications can be really helpful for readers all across the board.

However, many problems have been found within the application that could be improved. Firstly, the results show that the general search engine gives results that are too broad and it should be more precise.

Furthermore, although being a relatively small number, the HTML labeling algorithm should be improved or a redesign of the overall system should be held in order to reduce the number of sentences not labeled. This issue also affects the feature of the application that shows the parsed information about the references, preventing the display of some of them and decreasing the quality of the application.

In order to scale this prototype into a larger and more comprehensive application, a substantial increase in the number of articles processed should be applied. Articles from completely different fields and research areas should be added.

As suggested by some of the volunteers surveyed, the statistics section should be

clearer when it comes to its functionalities and what it displays. Furthermore, the existing features of the application could be improved to give a better performance across all devices.

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Appendix A

First Appendix

Figure 17: Histogram of answers for the general search question.

Figure 18: Histogram of answers for the faceted search question.

Figure 19: Results for the questions regarding the performance of the rhetorical class switches.

Is the reference number of the citation properly highlighted?

Figure 20: Answers given for the question regarding the highlighting of the inline citations.

Are the references properly highlighted?

Figure 21: Results for the question regarding the proper identification and highlighting of the references.

Did the selected reference appear in the "Selected Item" box?

Figure 22: Answers given for the question regarding the correct matching of each reference.

Are the items of the reference properly identified (Title, Authors, Journal, etc..)?

Figure 23: Histogram of answers for the accuracy of the individual identification of the elements in the references.

Do the links of the reference (DOI and Mendeley) appear?

Figure 24: Answers given for the question regarding the appearance of the DOI and URL of the reference.

Explore and Statistics section scores

Figure 25: Histogram of the answers for the evaluation of the Explore and Statistics sections.

Figure 26: Histogram of the answers for the evaluation of the overall application.

Figure 27: Histogram of ratios of found sentence.